

RESEARCH DIGEST

Impacts of the Inflation Reduction Act on the Economics of Clean Hydrogen and Synthetic Liquid Fuels

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The Inflation Reduction Act (IRA) in the United States provides unprecedented incentives for deploying low-carbon hydrogen and liquid fuels, among other low greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions technologies. To better understand the prospective competitiveness of low-carbon or negative-carbon hydrogen and liquid fuels under the IRA in the early 2030s, we examine the impacts of IRA provisions on costs of producing hydrogen and synthetic liquid fuel made from natural gas, electricity, short-cycle biomass (agricultural residues), and corn-ethanol. With IRA credits (45V or 45Q), but excluding incentives provided by other national or state policies, hydrogen produced by electrolysis using carbon-free electricity (green H₂) and natural gas reforming with carbon capture and storage (CCS) (blue H₂) are cost-competitive with the carbon-intensive benchmark gray H₂ from steam methane reforming. Biomass-derived H₂ with or without CCS is not cost-competitive under current IRA provisions. However, if IRA allowed biomass gasification with CCS to claim a 45V credit for carbon-neutral H₂ and a 45Q credit for negative biogenic-CO₂ emissions, this pathway would be less costly than gray H₂. The IRA credit for clean fuels (45Z), currently stipulated to end in 2027, would need to be extended, or similar policy support provided by other national or state policies, for clean synthetic liquid fuel to be cost-competitive with petroleum-derived liquid fuels. Levelized IRA subsidies per unit of CO₂ mitigated for all hydrogen and synthetic liquid fuel production pathways, except electricity-derived synthetic liquid fuel, range from 65 to 384 \$/t CO₂, which is within or below the range in U.S. federal government estimates of the Social Cost of Carbon (SCC) in the 2030 to 2040 timeframe.

In Princeton's Net-Zero America (NZA) study [1], electrification is a central feature of all modeled decarbonization pathways for the U.S. But liquid and gaseous fuels, including hydrogen (H₂) and synthetic liquid fuel (SLF), still account for 40% to 55% of final energy use in 2050, when the goal of economy-wide net-zero emissions is reached. To help understand the prospective competitiveness of different clean fuels, we carried out detailed lifecycle carbon and cost assessments of multiple technology pathways for producing clean fuels from natural gas, biomass, or electricity [2]. Subsequently, after passage of the Inflation Reduction Act (IRA), which provides unprecedented incentives for deploying low greenhouse gas emitting fuels, we extended the analysis to assess impacts of the IRA on hydrogen and liquid fuels. Other policies, such as the federal Renewable Fuel Standard (RFS) and various state policies, most notably California's Low Carbon Fuel Standard (LCFS) can be combined with IRA credits, and we also assess the impact of combining incentives for technologies, where relevant. We present plant-level techno-economic

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assessments to determine the levelized cost of fuel (LCOF) made via each of 15 different technological pathways (Table 1), taking into consideration provisions of the IRA, RFS, and LCFS. We also determined the levelized subsidies for carbon mitigation of IRA policies for evaluated technologies. We seek to answer the following questions:

- (1) Can the IRA incentives make them competitive on a production-cost basis in the 2030 timeframe with conventional, carbon-intensive fossil-fuel based equivalents?
- (2) Does the IRA appear to favor some production technology pathways over others?
- (3) Are there shortcomings in the design of the IRA incentives for production of these, and if so, what modifications might help mitigate those?

Methods

We evaluated 15 routes for H₂ and SLF production incorporating relevant IRA credits (Table 1). The hydrogen production pathways (P2-P6) may claim 45Q for carbon oxide capture and storage or use and 45V for low-carbon hydrogen production, while low-carbon liquid fuels can claim the 45Z credit. The IRA disallows any one facility from claiming more than one of 45V, 45Q, and 45Z credits. We interpret this as intended to prevent a facility from receiving a double benefit (e.g., blue hydrogen receiving both a 45V credit for hydrogen production and a 45Q credit for CO₂ sequestration). For P7 – P9 pathways, we assume these include separate clean hydrogen production (P2-P4), DAC for carbon-neutral CO₂, and RWGS-FTS facilities, with each receiving 45V or 45Q for hydrogen, 45Q for CO₂ utilization from DAC, or 45Z for liquid fuel, respectively. Similarly, P10 and P11 represent two facilities, one producing H₂ and CO₂ from biomass and garnering 45V credits and the other combining H₂ and CO₂ from the first facility to synthesize liquid fuels and collect 45Z credits. We also included integrated biomass gasification FT synthesis facilities with and without CCS (P12 and P13), which represent more efficient process to produce SLF but only receive a single IRA credit. In addition to FTS, we included two ethanol-to-jet pathways that upgrades ethanol to SLF without (P14) and with capturing and sequestering the fermentation CO₂.

Table 1. Hydrogen and Fischer-Tropsch liquids production pathways.*

Technology	Relevant IRA credits**
Hydrogen	
Path P1: Steam methane reforming (SMR)	N/A
P2: SMR with CO ₂ capture & storage (SMRCCS-H2)	45Q or 45V
P3: Autothermal reforming w/ CCS (ATRCCS-H2)	45Q or 45V
P4: Electrolysis using clean electricity (E-H2)	45V
P5: Biomass gasification H ₂ (BG-H2)	45V
P6: Biomass gasification H ₂ w/ CCS (BGCCS-H2)	45Q or 45V
Synthetic liquid fuels	
<i>Synthesis from carbon-neutral CO₂ and H₂</i>	
P7: H ₂ from P2 + CO ₂ from direct air capture (SMRCCS-H2 SLF)	45V, 45Q, 45Z
P8: H ₂ from P3 + CO ₂ from direct air capture (ATRCCS-H2 SLF)	45V, 45Q, 45Z
P9: H ₂ from P4 + CO ₂ from direct air capture (E-H2 SLF)	45V, 45Q, 45Z
P10: H ₂ from P5 + biogenic CO ₂ (BG-H2 SLF)	45V, 45Z
P11: H ₂ from P6 + biogenic CO ₂ (BGCCS-H2 SLF)	45V, 45Z
<i>Integrated biomass-gasification/FT synthesis</i>	
P12: Without CCS (Integrated BG-SLF)	45Z
P13: With CCS (Integrated BGCCS-SLF)	45Q or 45Z
<i>Ethanol-to-Synthetic liquid fuel</i>	
P14: Corn-ethanol to SLF	N/A
P15: Corn-ethanol w/ CCS to SLF	45Q and 45Z

* Pathways P1-P6 and P12-P14 represent production occurring at single facilities exploiting the single most remunerative IRA incentive among those for which they are eligible. Pathways P7-P9 are assumed to consist of 3 facilities each, which enables these pathways to incorporate 3

separate IRA credits: 45V or 45Q for H₂ production, 45Q for direct air capture, and 45Z for liquid fuel production. Pathways P10-P11 each include two facilities, one producing H₂ and CO₂ from biomass and garnering 45V credits and the other combining H₂ and CO₂ from the first facility to synthesize liquid fuels and collect 45Z credits. P 15 also represents two facilities, one capturing and sequestering fermentation CO₂ garnering 45Q and one produce SLF to collect 45Z credits.

** In addition to these listed credits, our analysis embeds IRA 45Y credits for clean electricity production into the assumed electricity price for pathway P4 and the IRA's stipulated penalties for methane emissions into the assumed natural gas price for pathways P1-P3. All pathways are assumed to satisfy prevailing wage and apprenticeship requirements and thus qualify for the maximum level of credit within a given type of IRA credit.

We determined levelized cost of fuel (\$/kg H₂ or \$/gal SLF) of all the technological routes with IRA subsidies. In addition, we compute levelized subsidies for CO₂ Mitigation (LSCM) implied in IRA credits for clean hydrogen or liquid fuel, which is determined by taking the sum of IRA credit (\$/kg H₂ or \$/gal SLF) divided by the CO₂ mitigation (kg CO₂e/kg H₂ or gal SLF) when clean H₂/SLF displace the carbon intensive benchmark (i.e., gray hydrogen and fossil-derived liquid fuel).

Findings

First, our analysis demonstrates that IRA subsidies will enable clean hydrogen to be cost-competitive with gray hydrogen. Under IRA, blue hydrogen will have costs comparable to gray hydrogen thanks to the 45Q credit for CCS. Green hydrogen receives the highest subsidies among all evaluated hydrogen pathways due to the combination of a 10-year 45Y renewable electricity PTC and a 10-year 45V hydrogen PTC, which make electrolysis the lowest cost option for hydrogen production. Biomass-derived hydrogen, however, is not cost-competitive despite IRA subsidies. In our analysis, we used attributional LCA and determined that green hydrogen had zero GHG emissions (Figure 1A) when carbon-free electricity sources are used. However, green hydrogen may result in consequential carbon emissions, when procurement of carbon-free electricity for hydrogen production leads other electricity users to switch to fossil generated power to meet their demands [3]. This raises concerns regarding the environmental benefits of green hydrogen, at least until the grid is fully decarbonized. It also raises the importance of rigorous standards for electricity procurement by grid-connected electrolyzers to ensure minimal direct or indirect emissions impacts.

Second, our results indicate that IRA incentives favor the electrolytic route to hydrogen over others (Figure 1B), subsidies for different hydrogen production pathways are observed to be approximately proportional to their GHG emissions reductions (\$76 /t CO₂e reduced), while the electrolysis route receives a disproportionately higher subsidy (\$217/t CO₂e). This suggests the IRA is intended to incentivize technology innovation as well as emissions reductions in the case of green hydrogen. A similar technology policy rationale could also reasonably apply to biomass gasification routes to hydrogen, but this is not the case under current IRA provisions.

Third, for liquid fuel pathways, we find that renewal and extension of the 45Z credit would be necessary for low and negative carbon emissions SLF production pathways to be competitive with petroleum-derived fuels. Low-carbon fuels producers would need to receive 45Z for a duration of 5+ years in order for three clean SLF routes to achieve LCOFs that fall within the recent historical range in U.S. wholesale jet fuel prices (Figure 2A), without considering the impact of any additional incentives (e.g., RFS or LCFS). We also find that stacking 45V and 45Z credits by artificially separating production facilities, e.g., BG-H₂ SLF (P10) and BGCCS-H₂ SLF (P11), provides for greater subsidies and results in a lower LCOF for SLF production from biomass than a single integrated facility, e.g., integrated Bio-SLF (P12) and BioCCS-SLF (P13), despite the higher capital costs and lower conversion efficiencies of biomass to fuel at separated production facilities. We further note that the IRA defines 45Z incentives to be a function of a pathway's life cycle GHG emissions. Accordingly, pathways with negative emissions

receive the highest credits per gallon of fuel produced. This raises the possibility that 45Z credits by themselves may incentivize less-efficient (i.e., BGCCS-SLF) over more-efficient (i.e., integrated BioCCS-SLF) bio-SLF production with CCS, because the lower efficiency enables greater CO₂ capture and storage to achieve stronger negative emissions. When federal RFS credits (RINs), which are available only to stand-alone biomass-SLF facilities (integrated Bio-SLF and BioCCS-SLF), are stacked with 45Z credits, the integrated BGCCS-SLF pathway could be sufficiently incentivized that it becomes less costly than the separated BGCCS-SLF pathway. In addition, LCFS credits can be stacked with IRA credits for any of the SLF pathways. For a wide array of combinations of 45Z duration, LCFS credit level, and RIN value, our analysis finds that the separated BGCCS-SLF (P11), Integrated Bio-SLF (P12), BioCCS-SLF (P13), and EtOHCCS-SLF (P15) pathways are the most cost-competitive compared to the median monthly-average wholesale price of jet fuel over the past decade (Figure 2B).

Finally, we find that IRA incentives for each pathway, when expressed in terms of levelized subsidies for carbon mitigation (LSCM), are below or within the range in the SCC estimated for 2030 to 2040, except for the electro-fuel pathway (P9), which receives a significantly higher total incentive due to stacking of multiple IRA credits (Figure 3). It is notable that, with IRA credits, BGCCS-H₂ (P6) is not cost-competitive with gray H₂ (P1) but has a LSCM well below the lower bound of the SCC range. We noted that if the IRA were to allow BGCCS-H₂ to simultaneously claim 45V credits for low-carbon hydrogen and 45Q credits for negative emissions, it would become cost-competitive with gray H₂, and the LSCM would still be below the lower bound of the SCC range.

In addition to the hydrogen and SLF pathways investigated in our analysis, one can envision other pathways to exploit stacking of credits to generate outside financial benefits, but with marginal environmental gains. For example, 45Y can be applied to carbon-free electricity generators to power electrolysis, 45V then provides \$3/kg H₂ to the electrolysis facility for its hydrogen production, and this hydrogen can end up in a hydrogen-fueled generator that could potentially claim a 45Y credit for its clean power generation. The system in this case intakes and produces carbon-free electricity, but the interior energy losses may be greater than another technology that performs the same service (e.g., battery electricity storage). For these reasons, policies that prioritize the use of fuels (hydrogen in particular) in sectors where there are no other alternatives or where decarbonization may be more challenging would be useful.

Figure 1. (A) Levelized cost of fuel production (LCOF), where positive values are costs and negative values are revenues from co-product sales or IRA credits, and life cycle GHG emissions for benchmark (P1.SMR) and five lower emissions hydrogen production pathways. Methane emission fees are embedded in our assumed natural gas price for P1- P3, and 45Y clean electricity credits are embedded in our assumed electricity price for P4. The life cycle GHG emissions for P1-P6 (assuming GWP₁₀₀ for non-CO₂ GHGs) are adopted from our previous analysis [2], and 142 GJ_{HHV}/kg H₂ is used to convert from kg CO₂e/GJ_{HHV} in [2] to kg CO₂e/kg H₂. IRA credits shown here are expressed as derated values to account for project economic lifetimes longer than the IRA-stipulated durations over which incentives are available, e.g., the \$ 1/kg H₂ and \$ 3/kg H₂ 45V credits are derated to \$ 0.8/kg H₂ and \$ 2.4/kg (See discussion around Eqn. 1 in Method.) (B) Levelized IRA subsidy values as a function of the life cycle GHG emissions reductions for clean hydrogen (P2-P6) versus the benchmark (P1).

Figure 2. (A) LCOF for SLF production pathways as a function of 45Z duration. The shaded region represents the range in monthly average wholesale jet fuel prices in the U.S. from 2012 to 2022: the lower bound is at the 10th percentile of the range (\$1.4/gal), and the upper bound is at the 90th percentile (\$3.72/gal). P14 is not shown on the graph because it is ineligible to receive 45Z and thus is insensitive to the duration of 45Z. (B) SLF production pathways that would be competitive with fossil jet fuel at 2.2 \$/gal under different 45Z durations, LCFS carbon credits, and RIN prices. All pathways (P7-P15) were considered in the analysis, but only P11, P12, P13, and P15 are competitive in the variable space examined here. P12 - P15 pathways are eligible for RIN credits (at 1.64 RIN credits per gallon). P14 and P15 are assumed to claim D6 and D5 RINs, respectively. Here we assume D6 and D5 RIN prices are the same. P12 and P13 are assigned D3 RINs, and the D3 price is the D5 price plus \$0.5 and \$1.5, which is the 25th and 75th percentile of the price difference between D3 RINs and D5 RINs in the past ten years. See Section 2 of the SI for discussion of RIN categories and prices.

Figure 3. Levelized subsidy for carbon mitigation (LSCM) implied in IRA credits for all evaluated pathways. The assumed duration of 45Q, 45V/45Y, and methane penalties are 12, 10, and 15 years, respectively. The duration of assumed 45Z credits is also taken to be 15 years. LSCM is the sum of IRA credits (\$/kg H₂ or \$/gal SLF) divided by the emissions avoided relative to fossil-derived hydrogen or jet fuel. The indicated range in Social Cost of CO₂ emissions (SCC) is for discount rates from 1.5% to 2.5% [4]. For 2030 and 2040, the SCC range is \$140 to 380/t CO₂ and \$170 to 430/t CO₂, respectively.

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